

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

An IR13240-108-4-2-3 line with leaf blast (BI) and brown planthopper (BPH) biotype 2 resistance in Angiang, Vietnam

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IR13240-108-4-2-3, a promising line from IRRI introduced in Angiang Province in 1983 and named MTL 58 by Cantho University, had good yields but was susceptible to leaf B1 and BPH biotype 2.

In the 1985 leaf B1 screening nursery at My Hoi Dong Village, Chomoi District, Angiang, three plants showed high resistance to leaf B1. We transplanted them, collected seeds, and multiplied at high speed. MTL 58 Tuyen (tuyen means selected) has good plant type, high tolerance for lodging, compact panicles, and long grain.

In farmers' field trials, it yielded 6-8 t/ha in the dry season and 5-6 t/ha in the wet season- 1 t/ha more than other varieties (see table).

It is resistant to lodging, has high response to N fertilizer, and is suitable for direct seeding and intensive farming.

It is susceptible to sheath blight and bacterial wilt, moderately susceptible to yellow stem borer. It has long and

slender grains and its cooking quality is acceptable to local consumers.

In the 1987 BPH nursery at Cantho University, MTL 58 Tuyen was resistant to BPH biotype 2.

MTL 58 Tuyen was released to farmers at the end of 1987. It has become the main variety in Angiang, planted on 80% of the irrigated and high yield area (200,000-240,000 ha/yr). □

MTL 58 Tuyen performance in dry season and wet season yield trials, Binh Duc, Angiang, Vietnam, 1987.

Characteristic	Dry season		Wet season	
	MTL 58 Tuyen	Mn 6A (check)	MTL 58 Tuyen	Mn 6A (check)
Duration (d)	113	118	114	114
Height (cm)	75	74	80	79
Lodging score	3	1	1	1
Stem borer deadhearts (%)	25	43	-	-
Panicles/m ²	383	515	356	499
Filled grains/panicle (no.)	66	52	43	20
1000-grain weight (g)	25.6	23.8	23.7	22.0
Yield (t/ha)	6.2	6.1	5.6	4.3
CV		5.9%		24.9%

Mandya Vijaya, a promising rice variety for summer in Bangalore Rural District

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Mandya Vijaya, from a cross of Sona and Mahsurie, has been released for general cultivation in tank and canal irrigated areas of Karnataka State. It is fine-grained, medium tall, with long duration.

We laid out 0.4-ha field demonstrations at three sites in Devanahally Taluk, Bangabre Rural District. Soils are Udic Paleustalfs, pH around 6.3, low in soluble salts, medium to low in organic C, low to medium in available P, medium to high in available K, and

adequate in DTPA-extracted Zn, Mn, Cu, Fe, and B.

Fertilizers to supply recommended NPK based on soil test were applied. Seed was sown in the nursery second week of Jan 1989 and 21-d-old seedlings were transplanted the second week of Feb. The crop took 160-164 d to maturity and yielded 6.3-7.0 t/ha. Other characters are given in the table.

We also studied the economics of cultivating Mandya Vijaya. Cost was

\$300-\$342/ha and net profit \$986-\$1,043/ha. The cost:benefit ratio was 1:4.1.

The major constraint to farmer adoption of this variety is its long duration: it does not suit farmers who have limited water resources. It gives higher yields in the summer season but delays normal sowing of the wet season rice crop or ragi *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn in a rice - ragi sequence. □

Grain yield, straw yield, duration, growth, yield characters, and economics of cultivation of Mandya Vijaya rice at 3 sites in Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Cost of cultivation (\$)	Gross returns ^a (\$)	Net returns (\$)	Cost:benefit ratio
Hunasamaranahally	7.0	13.5	160	88	10	145	319	1362	1043.0	1:4.2
Sadahally	7.0	13.8	164	85	11	130	342	1366	1024.0	1:3.9
Bhuvanahally	6.3	11.9	161	84	9	150	300	1286	986.0	1:4.3

^a Price/t rice=\$172.41 Price/t straw = \$11.49